

THE EFFECT OF MOBILE LEARNING IN TEACHING VOCABULARY.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6550927>

Fazliddinova Zulfiyakhon Dilmurod qizi

*Student of English filology, Namangan state
University, Namangan region, Uzbekistan.*

Abstract: *Smartphones have become an ordinary part of our lives, nowadays. The applications that these devices are utilized for are highly diverse, because of their incredible capacity. In terms of language instruction, the utilization of mobile apps has opened up new possibilities both for teachers and students. Teaching vocabulary became easier via mobile phone applications were introduced successfully. This article provides review of researches that were carefully collected from google scholars website.*

Keywords: *m-learning, vocabulary, application*

Introduction: With the advancement of technology in the twenty-first century, Internet, tablets, and smartphones are examples of advanced technologies. There are more creative methods for learning English. For instance, people can utilize technology to communicate messages, present information, and so on. Anytime, wherever, you can share information or thoughts. When individuals obtain a new smartphone these days, they almost always download apps (applications) right away. As a result, educators notice this trend and begin to create hundreds of applications for people to utilize in their daily lives. There have been several educational applications on the Internet over the past two decades. Teachers and students from all around the world may use applications to learn language faster.

By providing flexible, practical, and personalized opportunities of use in and outside the classroom, mobile learning challenges the conventional ways of teaching remarkably (Kukulaska-Hulme & Traxler, 2005 cited in Bazal, Yilmaz, 2016). Learning on the move is becoming more and more convenient, especially with smartphones that come with sophisticated hardware and software that makes them as competent as a computer. The large, touch-sensitive screens of today's smartphones, as Stockwell (2015, cited in Bazal, Yilmaz, 2016) pointed out, provide significant benefits over pre-smartphone mobile devices employed in various research (Hayati et al., 2013; Lu, 2008; Kukulaska-Hulme, 2010; Thornton & Houser, 2005).

Vocabulary learning is crucially important for foreign or second language learners' fluent communicative ability. Attention to vocabulary has been an integral part of the learning process for foreign language learners. This is particularly true

for Chinese English language learners who view vocabulary learning as the most important part of their linguistic competence enhancement noted Zhang, Song and Burston,(2011). According to Wang,(2017) the core of establishing skill and competency in a target language is vocabulary instruction. There has been a continuing quest to find the optimum method for teaching vocabulary. Although vocabulary is an important part of learning a foreign language in this circumstance, the most commonly used non-literal expressions are idiomatic expressions, and building blocks of daily discussions in a language, hence a lack of competence in using them can be detrimental, present challenges for language learners in terms of communication, such sounding strange and untrustworthy (Cooper, 1998, 1999,cited in Wang,2017).

noted Zhang, Song and Burston,(2011) studied the effect of m-learning,their Students studied a selected list of vocabulary via mobile phone SMS text messages while the paper group worked on the same list of vocabularies through paper material. Results showed that there was no significant difference ($p<.05$) in the posttests but not in the delayed tests. The study indicates that both of these approaches of vocabulary acquisition are beneficial in their own right, and that a combined approach to vocabulary learning may be more effective in terms of long-term retention rates.

1. Literature review

Vocabulary acquisition is critical for foreign or second language learners to communicate effectively. "Without grammar, very little can be expressed," Wilkins (1972, cited in Zhang, Song and Burston, 2011) said, "and without vocabulary, nothing at all can be conveyed" (p. 111). "If language structures make up the backbone of language, then it is language," Harmer (1994, cited in Zhang, Song and Burston, 2011) added "vocabulary that supplies critical organs and flesh". As vocabulary has unchangable place in language learning, teachers should instrust learners to learn as many words as they can.

However, learning new words is boring for children teachers are required to utilize interactive ways, one of the interactive and effective ways of teaching vocabulary may be teaching through mobile phones. Liaw and Huang says that because some components of learning are essentially mobile in the ways indicated above, portraying learning as a mobile activity does not differentiate it from other types of educational activities. We can better understand how knowledge and learning materials can be transported across settings such as homes and schools, how learning can be given and managed during life transitions, and how new technologies may be built to help education by focusing on learning mobility.(2009) Furthermore Lu notes that mobile phones 'are particularly useful computers that fit

in [a student's] pocket, are always with [students], and are nearly always on. The portability and immediacy allow students to learn in their preferred time and place (2008). Chinnery thinks that Internet connection, voice chatting, SMS text messaging, cameras, and even video recording are increasingly standard functions on the smartphones. All of these aspects enable conversational language practice, access to authentic information, and task fulfillment in language acquisition. Though such study is limited, it is not non-existent (2006).

Testing the effectiveness of mobile phones is very essential, and several scientists on this topic tested the use of smartphones. The Stanford Acquisition Lab, which investigated the use of mobile phones in language learning, established one of the earliest experiments on the topic (Brown, 2001, cited in Chinnery 2006). They created Spanish learning programs that combined voice and email communication with mobile phones. Vocabulary practice, tests, word and phrase translations, and access to live talking instructors were all included in these products. Their findings showed that if quizzes were presented in short chunks, mobile phones were successful; they also showed that automated voice vocabulary classes and quizzes had a lot of potential (Chinnery, 2006).

Basal, Yilmaz, ... (2016) compared the influence of teaching vocabulary between traditional way and using mobile devices according to them the goal of this four-week study was to evaluate the effectiveness of a mobile app for teaching 40 figurative idioms from the Michigan Corpus of Academic Spoken English (MICASE) corpus to traditional activities. The differences between the scores of the control (n=25) and experimental (n=25) groups established with convenience sampling were determined using a quasi-experimental study design with pretest and posttest. The experimental group fared much better in the posttest, confirming the usefulness of the mobile application utilized in this study for idiom learning. The research also makes recommendations for using mobile applications to teach vocabulary.

Yamaguchi (2005, cited in Chinnery, 2006) summarizes: "Although a computer is superior than a mobile phone in terms of managing different forms of information like as visual, auditory, and textual information, the mobile phone is superior to a computer in terms of speed portability. Furthermore, some kids may not have access to a computer." Therefore it is preferred to teach kids via SMS, or fascinating mobile applications.

Two groups of sophomores at a Chinese university were put into two intervention conditions by Zhang, Song and Burston (2011). The SMS group studied a selected list of vocabulary via mobile phone SMS text messages while the paper group worked on the same list of vocabularies through paper material in a

self-regulated manner. Results showed that there was a significant difference ($p < .05$) in the posttests but not in the delayed tests between the two groups. The study concluded that vocabulary learning through these two methods is effective in their own way and that a blended approach to vocabulary learning may better help increase the effectiveness.

Liaw, Hatala and Huang(2010) examined favorable aspects for m-learning system acceptability using an activity theory approach. They designed an m-learning system for learners' knowledge management in the study and asked 152 participants who were familiar with the system to report on their experience. The findings suggest that increasing learner happiness, fostering learner autonomy, empowering system functionalities, and enriching interaction and communication activities all have a good impact on m-learning system adoption.

Wu ,Chen and their friends(2012) performed meta-analysis to give more detailed examination of previous studies as a result the presented seven novel discoveries (1) The majority of mobile learning research focuses on efficacy, followed by the design of mobile learning systems. (2) Regardless of whether the study goal was assessment or design, surveys and experimental approaches were the favored research methodologies. (3) The results of mobile learning research are overwhelmingly favourable. (4) Although mobile phones and PDAs are the most popular devices for mobile learning, other developing technologies may eventually replace them. (5) Higher education institutions use mobile learning the most, followed by primary schools. (6) Professional students are the most typically supported by mobile learning.

Conclusion

Vocabulary is as crucial as grammar in language acquisition, therefore many researchers analyzed the effectiveness of m-learning in teaching vocabulary. According to the findings approximately 84 % of m-learning studies demonstrated positive outcomes.

REFERENCE:

1. Ahmet Basal, Selahattin Yilmaz, Asli Tanriverdi, & Lutfiye Sari, (2016) Effectiveness of Mobile Applications in Vocabulary Teaching CONTEMPORARY EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY, 2016, 7(1), 47-59
2. Bor-Tyng Wang, 2017 ,Designing Mobile Apps for English Vocabulary Learning, International Journal of Information and Education Technology, Vol. 7, No. 4, April 2017.

3. George M. Chinnery,(2006), EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES Going to the MALL: Mobile Assisted Language Learning, Language Learning & Technology <http://llt.msu.edu/vol10num1/emerging>, January, 2006, Volume 10, Number 1 pp. 9-16
4. Haisen Zhang, Wei Song, Jack Burston,(2011) REEXAMINING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF VOCABULARY LEARNING VIA MOBILE PHONES,TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology – July 2011, volume 10 Issue 3
5. M. Lu, (2008) Effectiveness of vocabulary learning via mobile phone Journal of Computer Assisted Learning (2008), 24, 515–525, doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2729.2008.00289.x
6. Shu-Sheng Liaw, Marek Hatala, Hsiu-Mei Huang, (2009), Investigating acceptance toward mobile learning to assist individual knowledge management: Based on activity theory approach, Computers & Education 54 (2010) 446–454, doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2009.08.029
7. Wen-Hsiung Wu, Yen-Chun Jim Wu, Chun-Yu Chen, Hao-Yun Kao, Che-Hung Lin, Sih-Han Huang,(2012), Review of trends from mobile learning studies: A meta-analysis, Computers & Education 59 (2012) 817–827

